

ANTI-HARASSMENT CHALLENGES IN CRIMINAL LAW

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Obviously harassment problems are circulated throughout the world. Organizations should talk about past experiences of harassment. The best way to deal with sexual crime is reduce fear of talking about it.

Management should demonstrate the importance of this issue, and the victim should not fear being fired or demoted. This issue concerns violence by men against women, women against men, as well as violence against women by women, and men against men. Violence is often driven by a desire for power. This is not only about sexual abuse, but also psychological abuse. All this undoubtedly affects the quality of a person's work and life.

Also government should focus their attention on implement international standards in this sphere. In particular some aspect of these standards had already been adopted in legislation by the government of Ukraine. For sure this is a crucial instrument to prevent sexual crime. However, as reality shows, this does deter neither people nor corporations from infringements.

Last but not the least, in this context, mediation and restorative practices will be effective, both in relation to specific cases and preventive sessions with the whole team or in groups.

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In 2015, world leaders agreed to 17 Global Goals – the *Sustainable Development Goals*. UNDP has made gender equality central to its work and we've seen remarkable progress in the past 20 years. According to Sustainable development goals (goal № 5) «Ending all discrimination against women and girls is not only a basic human right, it's crucial for sustainable future; it's proven that empowering women and girls helps economic growth and development» [1]. It could be agreed with this point.

However the problem of harassment is known all over the world and covers public places, work, etc. Some aspects of this issue have been studied in the works of scientists, in particular: O.V. Kharitonova, N.A. Savinova, V.O. Tuliakov, O.O. Uvarova. At the same time, the issue of harassment, particularly in the workplace, needs research.

There are more women than ever in the labor market, there are still large

inequalities in some regions, with women systematically denied the same work rights as men. Sexual violence and exploitation, the unequal division of unpaid care and domestic work, and discrimination in public office are remaining huge barriers [1].

Obviously countries all over the world are facing with this problem which has consequences for human, society and state. But how we can tackle this situation?

Significant changes have taken place in Ukraine in relation to criminal offenses against sexual freedom and inviolability. In accordance with the Law «On amendments to the Criminal and Criminal Procedure Codes of Ukraine in order to implement the provisions of the Council of Europe Convention on Preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence» of 6 December 2017 № 2227-VIII, significant changes were made to section «Crimes against sexual freedom and inviolability of the person». In particular, the approach to the definition of rape has changed significantly. According to the definition of the Criminal Code of Ukraine, before the amendments were made, the composition of rape provided for entering into natural sexual relations with the use of violence against the victim or the use of her helpless state. In the current version, sexual intercourse or other acts of a sexual nature with the victim (or victims) without consent has already constituted a rape (Article 152 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine). In this case, the absence of consent does not have to be related to resistance, it can be an orally «no».

The new legislative approach to the definition of rape is quite humanistic towards the victim, in line with the case law of the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR judgment in *MS v. Bulgaria* of 4 December 2003) and provides more opportunities for individuals in the context of sexual freedom. In addition, O.V. Kharitonova considers the above changes in the context of the new «optics» of Criminal law. In particular, «gender lenses provide conceptualization resources that allow for appropriate interpretations and relevant assessments» [2]. However, the views of scientists on such changes are different. Criticism of scholars is particularly related to the long-standing practice of this category of cases, which is not entirely related to the association of rape and refusal to have sex in the form of verbal «no» and without resistance to sexual intercourse or other sexual acts. It should also be noted that before the changes in practice there were also problems with qualification under Art. 152 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine, which were related especially to the detection of traces of violence during sexual intercourse, abuse by victims, etc.

Moreover, difficulties arise with the perception of «silent refusals».

According to the interpretation of the ECtHR practice, a person who has sexual intercourse should, among other things, not only not be refused, but also make sure that he agrees to have sexual intercourse. However, phrases that state uncertainty, such as «I do not know», «I am not sure», «maybe another time» also do not represent agreement and interpreted as «no». It should also be noted that a person may refuse not only before, but also in the process of sexual act.

Therefore, such changes reflect the European concept of a culture of consent, which is a promising, civilized and humanistic step. However, in the presence of uncertainties in criminal law, they can open up a field of abuse by victims.

Harassment in the workplace. General Recommendation № 19 of the UN Convention on the Elimination of all forms of discrimination against women states that «sexual harassment includes such undesirable sexual behaviors as physical contact and suggestions, sexual innuendos, pornography, and sexual demands committed by words or deeds. Such behavior can be offensive and can endanger health and safety; it is discriminatory when a woman has good reason to believe that her refusal might be harmful her employment and promotion, or when it creates a hostile environment at work» [3].

The Law of Ukraine «On ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men» defines sexual harassment as «sexual acts expressed verbally (threats, intimidation, obscene remarks) or physically (touching, slapping), humiliating or insulting persons in a relationship labor, service, material or other subordination» [4]. Article 154 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine «Forcing to sexual intercourse» provides criminal responsibility for forcing a person without his or her voluntary consent to sexual act with another person. Qualified corpus delicti provides criminal responsibility for forcing a person without his or her voluntary consent to sexual act with another person from whom the victim is financially or professionally dependent. The crime is punished by a fine of up to 1,000 tax-free minimum incomes or imprisonment for up to two years. Thus, not only the relationship of material or service subordination has already taken into account.

It is worth noting that European law goes by establishing responsibility for the harassment of any employee, not just the manager. The Explanatory report to the European Social Charter emphasizes that sexual harassment is unwanted sexual behavior on the part of management and colleagues, which affects the dignity of workers. In fact, in most cases, the perpetrator is not the leader and has the same status in the organization as the victim. Obscene jokes, comments or questions of a sexual nature, touches, hugs, kisses are extremely common in offices, but, unfortunately, only a fraction of people recognize them as an offense

for which there is legal liability.

Rose L. Siuta, Mindy E. Bergman said «Well-documented workplace effects of sexual harassment include reduced job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and productivity, and increased job stress, turnover, withdrawal, and conflict. Sexual harassment negatively affects target’s psychological and physical well-being, including increases in post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), depression, and anxiety symptoms, emotional exhaustion, headaches, sleep problems, gastric distress, and upper respiratory problems. All of these individual-level effects can result in financial decrements for the target and the organization. Organizational climates that are more tolerant of sexual harassment produce more sexual harassment. Those with lower organizational power are more likely to experience sexual harassment, particularly by people with higher levels of power; however, contrapower harassment (harassment of individuals with higher organizational power by those with lower organizational power) can also occur» [5]. I guess countering workplace harassment is one of the crucial point for government.

On February 18, 2021, the Law of Ukraine № 1256-IX On amendments to certain legislative acts of Ukraine concerning the implementation of the Council of Europe Convention for the Protection of children against sexual exploitation and sexual violence (Lanzarote Convention) was adopted. According to criminalized article 156-1 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine, «an adult person is criminally liable for offering to meet, including using information and telecommunications systems or technology, to a person under the age of sixteen, with the aim of commit any sexual or lewd acts against him or her, if, after such proposal, at least one action has been taken to ensure that a meeting takes place. According to the note to this article, a meeting should understand, including a meeting, which involves the use of information and telecommunications systems or technologies». These are important changes for Ukrainian criminal law, given the development of information technology, the diversity of communication methods and their accessibility, including for children. However, the harassment of adults is not currently criminalized.

The Spanish government intends to change the definition of consent in a law that equates victims of sexual violence with victims of gender-based violence. The proposal has already been submitted to the Council of Ministers and takes into account the criminalization of street harassment» [6]. This year, the Bundestag recognized **upskirting** (photo and video shooting under the skirt) as a criminal offense. Another step against discrimination against women could be the criminalization of catcalling [7].

A 20-year-old German student initiated a petition on the topic of **catcalling**, which has already been signed by more than 65,000 people. Catcalling is a type of street harassment. The activist believes that the phenomenon demonstrates the dominance and power of men, and suggests according to a survey conducted by the Foundation for European Progressive Studies, two-thirds of women in Germany at least once in their lives have encountered whistling in the streets, and more than 40% – with comments, ridicule, sexist images or gestures of a sexual nature. In France such «compliments» is punished by a fine of € 750. Catcalling is illegal in Belgium, the Netherlands and Portugal as well.

The gang rape known as the «La Manada» case has had an unprecedented social impact in Spain. N. I. Mondragon, L. G. Echaide, N. A. Alcibar & M. L. Eguileor recognized that 6,592 tweets with the hashtag #lamanada were selected and their content was analyzed by lexical analysis using Iramuteq software. The results reveal both an awareness phase about the issue along with a divergence phase that saw the emergence of various interpretations about this case, which were confronted. In this divergence phase, feminist discourses took on great significance, expressing anger, calling for social mobilizations, criticizing the victim blaming and creating a dialogue against rape culture. However, the anti-feminist and sexist discourses were also present in this space. It is concluded that discourses on Twitter are a symptom of a shift in mentality whilst at the same time serve as an active constructor of this changed knowledge [8]. I find this a pretty interesting approach to researching social issues about crime.

In conclusion I am confident that organizations should talk about past experiences of harassment. The best way to deal with sexual crime is reduce fear of talking about it.

For instance, administration should demonstrate the importance of this issue, and the victim should not fear being fired or demoted. This issue concerns violence by men against women, women against men, as well as violence against women by women, and men against men. Violence is often driven by a desire for power. This is not only about sexual abuse, but also psychological abuse. All this undoubtedly affects the quality of a person's work and life.

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References:

1. What are the Sustainable Development Goals? [Access: 21.12.2021] Available: <https://www.undp.org/sustainable-development-goals#gender-equality>
2. KHARYTONOVA O.V. KLYUCHOVI, Zasady hendernoyi polityky v kryminal'nomu pravi Ukrayiny ta osnovni napryamy reform shchodo protydyiyi nasyt'stvu stosovno zhinok ta domashn'omu nasyt'stvu: nauk.-prakt. posibnyk. Kharkiv: Prava lyudyny, 2018. 280 p.
3. General recommendations made by the Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women № 1-37 [Access: 21.12.2021] Available: <https://www.un.org/womenwatch/daw/cedaw/recommendations/recomm.htm>
4. Zakon Ukrayiny № 2866-IV vid 8 veresnya 2005 r. «Pro zabezpechennya rivnykh prav ta mozhlyvostey zhinok ta cholovikiv». 2005. [Access: 21.12.2021] Available: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2866-15#Text>
5. ROSE L. SIUTA, MINDY E. BERGMAN. Sexual Harassment in the Workplace. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190224851.013.191>. Published online: 25 June 2019. [Access: 21.12.2021]. Available: <https://oxfordre.com/business/view/10.1093/acrefore/9780190224851.001.0001/acrefore-9780190224851-e-191>
6. KHOZHAINOVA V. Ispaniya khoche kryminalizuvaty vulychne domahannya. Shcho za n'oho zahrozhuvatyme. [Access: 21.12.2021] Available: <https://suspilne.media/187468-u-francii-zatrimali-pidozruvanogo-u-vbivstvi-zurnalista-hasoggi/>
7. Nebezpechni komplimenty. Zakon ta biznes. 2020. [Access: 21.12.2021] Available: https://zib.com.ua/ua/145628-nimechchina_mozhe_viznati_zlochinom_slovesni_domagannya.html
8. MONDRAGON N., ECHAIDE L., ALCIBAR N. & EGUILEOR. M. “La Manada” in the digital sphere: coping with a sexual aggression case through Twitter, Feminist Media Studies, 20:7, 926-943, 2020. DOI: 10.1080/14680777.2019.1643387. [Access: 21.12.2021] Available: <https://www.tandfonline.com/action/showCitFormats?doi=10.1080%2F14680777.2019.1643387>

